

Rewriting the Past for the Present: A Computational Study of Sitcom Presentism using Fine-Tuned Language Models

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Abstract

We model *presentism* (reinterpreting past artefacts through contemporary horizons [1, 2]) as a computational pipeline that updates 1990s *Seinfeld* plots to read plausibly in 2025 while preserving comedic beats and ensemble dynamics. Stage (1) rewrites Wikipedia-style outlines into 4–8-beat 2025 plot sketches with a style card and the exact stop marker `### Plot End`. Stage (2) uses a high-precision NER prompt to extract entities in a fixed 18-key schema, deduplicated with fallbacks. Stage (3) builds entity-aware IO pairs and fine-tunes **Qwen2.5-14B-Instruct** with PEFT (AdaLoRA) in 4-bit NF4. Averaging five independent 4-fold evaluations (20 runs total), final loss is **1.336** (std **0.040**); best loss **1.329** (std **0.036**). Outputs are compact (mean length \approx **181** tokens), semantically coherent with inputs (**0.553** cosine), and show low lexical overlap (Jaccard **0.132**). Diversity remains high (**distinct-2 = 0.721**; **distinct-3 = 0.927**). Materials, prompts, and evaluation scripts will be released via [GitHub Repository](#).

Keywords: presentism; sitcoms; large language models; fine-tuning; digital humanities

Approach and Results

Data and preprocessing. We use public Wikipedia-style episode summaries (not dialogue) to steer modelling toward plot-level rewriting and reduce copyright risk. Pre-modernization applies a PG-13 style card (2023–2025 references; NYC details) with temperature 0.8, top- p 0.92, a 320-token cap, and fallback for very short generations. NER returns strict JSON with 18 keys; empty `characters/places` trigger capitalised-span fallbacks. Flattened entities (max 40) seed IO prompts; targets are the modernised plot plus `### Plot End`.

Model and training. Base model is Qwen2.5-14B-Instruct in 4-bit NF4 with bfloat16 compute. We use AdaLoRA (LoRA fallback), 8 epochs, LR 7×10^{-5} , cosine schedule (warmup 0.1), batch size 1 with accumulation 16, gradient checkpointing, and no checkpoint saves (metrics/logs only).

Evaluation. We report per-fold final/best losses, continuity (mean word count), unigram Jaccard, semantic coherence (`all-MiniLM-L6-v2`), and `distinct-n`. Table 1 and Figure 1 show low lexical overlap alongside moderate semantic coherence.

Interpretation. The model preserves story intent and character dynamics (semantic coherence) while avoiding surface reuse (low Jaccard), operationalising presentism as cultural adaptation rather than repetition.

Example (as used in our pipeline): “The Invitations”

Prompt + Context (Original episode summarised for space)

You are a sitcom plot writer updating legacy episode `*plots*` to feel current in 2025.
 Keep core character dynamics and comedic beats, but:

Table 1: Averaged results across five repetitions of the 4-fold evaluation (20 total runs). Values are mean \pm std. Lower loss and higher diversity indicate improved stylistic control. The variable n denotes the number of plots in each test fold.

Fold	final_loss	best_loss	continuity	Jaccard	Sem. coh.	distinct-2	distinct-3	n
0	1.422	1.409	166.700	0.118	0.495	0.714	0.922	43
1	1.288	1.285	192.300	0.134	0.580	0.717	0.925	43
2	1.382	1.377	172.800	0.133	0.537	0.723	0.929	43
3	1.252	1.248	188.400	0.147	0.590	0.730	0.936	42
Mean (5\times4 avg)	1.336	1.329	181.0	0.132	0.553	0.721	0.927	—
Std (pooled)	0.040	0.036	—	—	—	—	—	—

Figure 1: Per-fold means showing low lexical overlap and moderate semantic coherence. Dashed lines mark the overall mean (0.132, 0.553).

- Update references (e.g. tech, social platforms, slang, brands, news) to feel 2025.
- Swap outdated devices with modern equivalents (e.g. DMs, group chats, ride-hailing, wireless earbuds).
- Use contemporary New York details (e.g. contactless payments, delivery apps, e-bikes, remote/hybrid work).
- Avoid anachronisms. Prefer 2023-2025 references.

Directive: Produce a sitcom *plot outline* (not script). <|era_2025|>
 Length window: 160-320 tokens. End with the exact line: **### Plot End**

Original episode note: Season 7 finale resolving George’s engagement arc; Jerry becomes engaged to a like-minded partner; friends intervene as the wedding nears. Please modernise to 2025 and conclude with **### Plot End**.

Updated plot outline (verbatim from our run).

Plot: “*The Invitations*”

- George still doesn’t want to marry Susan, now a TikTok influencer known for her bizarre challenges. They’re planning their wedding, with George trying every desperate measure to get out of it. He confides in Jerry, Elaine, and Kramer about his woes via group chat.
- Jerry gets engaged to a woman who’s the perfect match—she’s a podcaster who shares all his interests, even his disdain for contactless payments and preference for e-bike rides over

scooters. She's also a fan of Jerry's stand-up comedy shows.

- When George meets Susan's mom at a coffee shop, she insists they use a new app to order drinks and pay contactlessly. George struggles with the tech, adding to his frustration.
- Elaine, now working remotely from home, suggests George stage a fake breakup through DMs on a group chat with Susan's friends. George goes too far, sending a rant that Susan sees as a breakup announcement.
- At a dinner party, George tries to convince Susan to call off the wedding by mentioning his latest dating app hookup, a fitness trainer who's into vintage video games. Susan, annoyed, says she'll only consider it if George can prove he's genuinely unhappy.
- George, feeling cornered, awkwardly uses a smart speaker to play a breakup song while Susan's mom is nearby, leading to an embarrassing moment where everyone hears the song.
- Jerry's fiancée turns out to be a big fan of his ex-girlfriend, much to Jerry's dismay. He realizes she might...

Ethics, Data Provenance, and Limitations

Episode summaries were sourced from the public Wikipedia [List of Seinfeld episodes](#) (CC BY-SA 4.0). We used factual summaries instead of scripts to avoid replicating copyrighted creative language. Each modernised plot and NER list was manually checked for plausibility, alignment, and label accuracy. We disclose prompts, parameters, and evaluation metrics but not model weights or bulk outputs. Parameter-efficient fine-tuning limited compute. Limitations include a single series, English-only corpus, and automated coherence metrics as proxies for humour and style.

References

- [1] François Hartog. *Regimes of historicity: Presentism and experiences of time*. Columbia University Press, 2015.
- [2] David Lowenthal. *The past is a foreign country—revisited*. Cambridge University Press, 2015.